

STUDENT TEACHERS' ASSESSMENT OF THE IN-HOUSE LICENSURE EXAMINATION REVIEW PROGRAM-EFFECTIVENESS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of the in-house licensure examination for teachers review program as perceived by student teachers. The study utilized a descriptive-evaluative research design to assess the effectiveness of the in-house licensure examination for teachers review program at Foundation University. It also aimed to identify areas for improvement to guide the development of a more effective review program. The study focused on five key dimensions: (a) content, relevance, and coverage; (b) delivery and instruction; (c) organization and management; (d) student motivation and confidence; and (e) outcomes and satisfaction. Data were gathered from 77 student teachers enrolled in the College of Education during Academic Year 2024–2025 through a researcher-developed, expert-validated Google Form survey. Ethical research standards were strictly observed, with approval secured from the College of Education prior to data collection. Results indicated high overall effectiveness across all dimensions; however, certain areas such as organization and scheduling revealed lower mean scores, suggesting opportunities for refinement. The findings provide valuable information for enhancing program quality and ensuring student teachers' preparedness for licensure examinations.

Keywords: *licensure examination, review program evaluation, teacher education, program improvement*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher licensure examinations serve as critical benchmarks in determining the competence, qualification, and readiness of future educators. Globally, they are recognized as essential mechanisms to ensure that teachers possess the necessary proficiency to deliver quality education (Jaekel *et al.*, 2022; Tabroni *et al.*, 2022; Yauney, 2022). In the Philippines, the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is a mandatory requirement for entry into the teaching profession and is considered a key indicator of teacher education program effectiveness.

Recognizing the importance of licensure performance, Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) across the country have implemented various support mechanisms to enhance student preparedness for the LET. These initiatives are aligned with national policies and frameworks such as the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), CHED Memorandum Order No. 52, s. 2007, and DepEd Orders No. 32, s. 2009, and No. 42, s. 2017. Among these interventions is the conduct of in-house review programs, which are often faculty-led efforts to bridge the gap between academic preparation and professional practice. These review programs aim not only to reinforce content mastery in general, professional, and major education subjects but also to build student teachers' confidence, motivation, and test-taking strategies (Colicol *et al.*, 2021).

At the College of Education, the in-house licensure examination review program was initiated to support student teachers in improving their chances of success in the LET. This program is driven by the institution's commitment to contribute to Sustainable Development Goal No. 4 on Quality Education, and to enhance teacher readiness and competence before they enter the field. While participation in the review and pass rates may indicate success to some extent, these alone do not fully capture the effectiveness of the program. As the primary beneficiaries, student teachers offer a critical perspective in evaluating the strengths and areas for improvement of the review program.

This study seeks to assess the effectiveness of the in-house licensure examination review program from the perspective of student teachers. Specifically, it examines the program in terms of content relevance and coverage, delivery and instruction, organization and management, student motivation and confidence, and overall satisfaction. The insights gathered will provide a valuable basis for refining the program, guiding institutional decision-making, and ultimately enhancing the professional readiness and licensure success of future educators.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the in-house licensure examination review program as perceived by student teachers. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How effective is the review program in terms of content relevance and coverage?

2. How effective is the review program in terms of delivery and instruction?
3. How effective is the review program in terms of organization and management?
4. How effective is the review program in promoting student motivation and confidence?
5. How effective is the review program in terms of overall outcomes and satisfaction?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-evaluative research design to provide a comprehensive assessment of the in-house licensure examination review program. It was descriptive because it examined student teachers' perceptions of the program's effectiveness across five key areas: (a) content, relevance, and coverage; (b) delivery and instruction; (c) organization and management; (d) student motivation and confidence; and (e) outcomes and satisfaction. This approach enabled the systematic measurement and summary of trends in students' feedback, ensuring the relevance and overall quality of the program.

Meanwhile, it was evaluative because it determined the effectiveness of the program based on the student teachers' judgments, allowing for a critical appraisal of its strengths and areas for improvement. Through this dual approach, the study not only documented the participants' perceptions but also provided actionable insights and recommendations to enhance the quality and impact of the review program in preparing student teachers for the licensure examination.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the Foundation University College of Education (FUCE), located along Dr. Miciano Road, Taclobo, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, Philippines. FUCE is a recognized teacher education institution, accredited at Level III by the Philippine Association of Colleges and Universities Commission on Accreditation (PACUCOA), an indication of its commitment to academic excellence and continuous quality improvement in teacher education.

The college offers a range of undergraduate degree programs in education, including the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd) and the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) with specializations in English, Filipino, Science, Social Studies, Values Education, and Mathematics. It also offers programs in Bachelor of Physical Education and Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education, aimed at equipping future educators with the pedagogical knowledge, skills, and values essential for professional teaching practice.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 77 student teachers from the College of Education who were enrolled in A.Y. 2024–2025 at Foundation University and had completed the in-house licensure examination review program. They were selected as respondents because they had direct experience with the program and could provide informed feedback on its effectiveness.

All student teachers invited to participate responded to the survey, resulting in a 100% response rate. Data were gathered through a Google Form, ensuring accessibility and ease of participation. The full participation of the target group enhanced the reliability of the findings and provided a comprehensive account of student teachers' perceptions regarding the review program.

Research Instrument

The primary research instrument used in this study was a researcher-designed Google Form survey, structured to assess student teachers' perceptions of the in-house licensure examination review program. The survey consisted of both quantitative and qualitative components.

The Likert-scale items were designed to measure the perceived effectiveness of the program which include the five key areas: a) Content, Relevance, and Coverage, b) Delivery and Instruction, c) Organization and Management, d) Student Motivation and Confidence, and e) Outcomes and Satisfaction. Each area was evaluated using clearly defined indicators to ensure consistency and reliability in responses.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection commenced after the respondents' consents were confirmed. The data for this study were gathered using a self-administered Google Form survey specifically designed to evaluate student teachers' perceptions of the in-house licensure examination review program. Prior to distribution, the survey instrument was reviewed by academic experts to ensure content validity and clarity. Revisions were made accordingly to guarantee that all items were relevant and aligned with the research objectives.

Once the instrument was finalized, coordination with the College of Education student teacher coordinators was carried out to facilitate the dissemination of the Google Form to all student teachers who had completed the review program. An orientation was provided, prior to administering the questionnaires to explain the purpose of the study, ensure informed consent, and emphasize the voluntary nature of participation.

The Google Form contained both specific indicators for each of the component being assessed and a 5-point Likert scale is utilized for quantitative data and an open-ended section for qualitative input. The survey link was distributed through the official group chat for student teachers, and they were given a specified period to complete the form.

The entire process was conducted with strict adherence to ethical standards. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. All student teachers responded to the survey, resulting in a 100% response rate. Data were automatically recorded and securely stored through the Google platform (Excel) which can be downloaded for analysis.

To analyze the data gathered from student teachers regarding their assessment of the in-house licensure examination review program, the researchers employed descriptive statistical tools. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize the participants' responses across the five key areas: content relevance and coverage, delivery and instruction, organization and management, student motivation and confidence, and outcomes and satisfaction. These tools helped identify the overall perceptions and levels of agreement among the respondents. The use of these statistical tools provided a comprehensive and reliable evaluation of the effectiveness of the program and guided the formulation of relevant recommendations for improvement.

Statistical Tools

The researchers utilized the mean and standard deviation to analyze the data. The mean was used to determine the extent of the review program's effectiveness in terms of content relevance and coverage, delivery and instruction, organization and management, student motivation and confidence, outcomes and satisfaction, and overall effectiveness. Meanwhile, the standard deviation was employed to measure the variability in the responses of the student teachers.

RESULTS

Table 1. Extent of Effectiveness of the Review Program as Perceived by Student Teachers in terms of Content, Relevance, and Coverage (N=77)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. The review content aligns with the LET curriculum.	4.45	SA	VH	0.73
2. Practice questions and drills enhance the mastery of the subject.	4.25	SA	VH	0.87
3. Sample test items reflect the actual LET questions.	4.20	A	H	0.82
4. Review materials are comprehensive and useful.	4.14	A	H	0.88
5. There is sufficient time for each subject area.	3.51	A	H	1.23
Composite	4.11	A	H	0.91

Note: Verbal Description (VD), Extent of Effectiveness (EoE); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Neutral (N), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 1 displays that the review program is perceived as highly effective, yielding a composite mean of 4.11 (SD = 0.91). The highest-rated indicators include alignment of

the review content with the LET curriculum ($\bar{x} = 4.45$), enhancement of mastery through drills and practice items ($\bar{x} = 4.25$), and the use of sample test items aligned with the LET format ($\bar{x} = 4.20$). Students also rated the comprehensiveness of the review materials ($\bar{x} = 4.14$) and the adequacy of content coverage as highly effective. The indicator on time allocation per subject area obtained the lowest mean ($\bar{x} = 3.51$) but remains within the “high effectiveness” range.

Table 2. Extent of Effectiveness of the Review Program as Perceived by Student Teachers in terms of Delivery and Instruction (N=77)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. Review facilitators are knowledgeable and competent.	4.42	SA	VH	0.77
2. Instructional methods are clear and effective.	4.21	SA	VH	0.77
3. Facilitators use real LET-type items effectively.	4.20	A	H	0.75
4. Complex topics are simplified during the review.	4.18	A	H	0.74
5. Sessions are interactive and engaging.	3.86	A	H	0.87
Composite	4.17	A	H	0.78

Note: Verbal Description (VD), Extent of Effectiveness (EoE); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Neutral (N), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 2 indicates a composite mean of 4.17 (SD = 0.78), showing high effectiveness in delivery and instruction. The highest ratings are given to facilitators’ expertise and competence ($\bar{x} = 4.42$) and clarity of instructional methods ($\bar{x} = 4.21$). Students also agreed that facilitators effectively used LET-type questions ($\bar{x} = 4.20$) and simplified complex topics ($\bar{x} = 4.18$). Engagement and interactivity during sessions received the lowest rating ($\bar{x} = 3.86$), although this still indicates high effectiveness.

Table 3. Extent of Effectiveness of the Review Program as Perceived by Student Teachers in terms of Organization and Management (N=77)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. Session reminders and updates are posted in GC.	4.41	SA	VH	0.87
2. Materials are provided.	4.24	SA	VH	0.90
3. Facilitators use real LET-type items effectively.	3.86	A	H	1.16
4. There is efficient time management during sessions.	3.72	A	H	0.94
5. The schedule is well-organized.	3.70	A	H	0.88
Composite	3.99	A	H	0.95

Note: Verbal Description (VD), Extent of Effectiveness (EoE); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Neutral (N), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 3 presents a composite mean of 3.99 (SD = 0.95), signifying high effectiveness in organization and management. The highest-rated indicator is the communication of reminders and updates through the group chat ($\bar{x} = 4.41$). Availability of review materials is also rated highly ($\bar{x} = 4.24$). Lower ratings are observed for time management during

sessions ($\bar{x} = 3.72$) and organization of the program schedule ($\bar{x} = 3.70$), although both remain within the high range.

Table 4. Extent of Effectiveness of the Review Program as Perceived by Student Teachers in terms of Student Motivation and Confidence (N=77)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. The review promotes self-assessment and reflection.	4.24	SA	VH	0.89
2. The review program boosted my confidence for LET.	3.99	A	H	0.89
3. Practice tests help lessen my anxiety.	3.93	A	H	0.98
4. I became more motivated to study due to the review.	3.90	A	H	0.99
5. I feel more prepared to take the LET.	3.72	A	H	0.94
Composite	3.95	A	H	0.94

Note: Verbal Description (VD), Extent of Effectiveness (EoE); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Neutral (N), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 4 reflects a composite mean of 3.95 (SD = 0.94), indicating high effectiveness in enhancing motivation and confidence. The highest-rated indicator is the promotion of self-assessment and reflection ($\bar{x} = 4.24$). Other indicators such as increased confidence ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), reduced anxiety through practice tests ($\bar{x} = 3.93$), and improved motivation to study ($\bar{x} = 3.90$) also received high ratings. Feeling prepared for the LET obtained the lowest rating ($\bar{x} = 3.72$), though still classified as highly effective.

Table 5. Extent of Effectiveness of the Review Program as Perceived by Student Teachers in terms of Outcomes and Satisfaction (N=77)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. The review helped improve my content mastery.	4.24	SA	VH	0.93
2. I believe this review contributes to LET readiness.	4.17	A	H	0.93
3. I would recommend this review to others.	4.15	A	H	1.02
4. The review addressed my individual learning needs.	4.14	A	H	0.93
5. The program met my expectations.	3.96	A	H	0.96
Composite	4.13	A	H	0.95

Note: Verbal Description (VD), Extent of Effectiveness (EoE); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Neutral (N), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 5 shows a composite mean of 4.13 (SD = 0.95). Improvement in content mastery obtained the highest rating ($\bar{x} = 4.24$). Students also reported enhanced readiness for the LET ($\bar{x} = 4.17$) and willingness to recommend the program ($\bar{x} = 4.15$). Addressing individual learning needs ($\bar{x} = 4.14$) is also rated highly. The lowest indicator, meeting student expectations, received a mean of 3.96.

Table 6. Overall Effectiveness of the Review Program as Perceived by Student Teachers (N=77)

Variables	\bar{x}	VD	EoE	SD
1. Content, Relevance and Coverage	4.11	A	H	0.91
2. Delivery and Instruction	4.17	A	H	0.78
3. Organization and Management	3.99	A	H	0.95
4. Student Motivation and Confidence	3.95	A	H	0.94
5. Outcomes and Satisfaction	4.13	A	H	0.95

Note: Verbal Description (VD), Extent of Effectiveness (EoE); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61-3.40, Neutral (N), Moderate (M); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00-1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD), Very Low (VL)

Table 6 reveals consistently high mean scores across five dimensions: delivery and instruction ($\bar{x} = 4.17$), outcomes and satisfaction ($\bar{x} = 4.13$), content relevance and coverage ($\bar{x} = 4.11$), organization and management ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), and student motivation and confidence ($\bar{x} = 3.95$). All dimensions fall within the “high effectiveness” range.

DISCUSSION

Content, Relevance and Coverage

The high ratings indicate that the College of Education has effectively designed a review program aligned with LET expectations. Alignment with curriculum standards supports Valle and Brobo (2022), who report that structured review interventions for BEED and BSED students enhance conceptual preparation. The high effectiveness of LET-type drills further supports Lopez and Viswanathappa (2025), who emphasize the importance of aligning curriculum content with assessment demands. The comparatively lower rating for time allocation suggests a need for improved pacing. This concern reflects the findings of Resch *et al.* (2022), who argue that limited instructional time constrains the application of theory to practice. Addressing pacing and time allotment may further strengthen the review program.

Delivery and Instruction

The high effectiveness of facilitators and instructional clarity aligns with Annan-Brew *et al.* (2024), who highlight the value of structured delivery and scaffolding in supporting pre-service teachers’ learning. The strong alignment between instructional practices and LET standards emphasizes the authenticity of the approach. The lower rating for session engagement suggests the need for more interactive and participatory strategies. This aligns with Kausar and Ajmal (2024), who note that interactive communication skills often require strengthening in teacher education programs.

Organization and Management

Strong ratings for communication and availability of materials reflect effective logistical support, consistent with Almazroa and Alotaibi (2023), who highlight the importance of structured information systems in review environments. The lower ratings for scheduling and time management echo concerns raised by Resch *et al.* (2022) regarding the impact of inefficient timing on learning transfer. These findings reinforce Valle and Brobo's (2022) conclusion that efficient coordination and resource management are crucial to optimizing review program outcomes.

Student Motivation and Confidence

The program's support for reflection, motivation, and reduced anxiety aligns with Fiscal and Roman (2022) and Villaflores (2023), who emphasize the importance of structured interventions in enhancing LET preparedness. Reflective practices supported by the program are consistent with Resch *et al.* (2022), while confidence-building aligns with findings by Kausar and Ajmal (2024). The lower perceived readiness rating mirrors Albite's (2019) observation that simulated tests enhance metacognitive awareness, prompting students to recognize their learning needs. This suggests the need for continued practice, feedback, and confidence-building initiatives.

Outcomes and Satisfaction

High ratings affirm that the program effectively enhances content mastery and LET readiness, consistent with Heretape and Paglinawan (2024). The program's responsiveness to diverse needs aligns with Kausar and Ajmal's (2024) emphasis on differentiated instruction. The slightly lower rating for meeting expectations suggests the need for more tailored enhancements, similar to the recommendations of Reyes-Chua *et al.* (2023), who advocate continuous improvement in review programs.

Overall Effectiveness

The consistently high effectiveness across all dimensions reinforces the program's strong contribution to LET readiness, aligning with Paz *et al.* (2024), who found in-house LET review sessions to significantly improve pre-service teacher performance. Delivery and instruction stand out as major strengths, supporting Lopez and Viswanathappa's (2025) argument on the importance of competent facilitation. Lower but still high ratings for organization and motivation highlight areas for refinement. These findings echo Andrecio *et al.* (2023) and suggest that improved scheduling, logistics, and confidence-building initiatives may further enhance program effectiveness.

Conclusions

The in-house licensure examination review program is generally perceived by student teachers as highly effective across multiple dimensions. The consistently high ratings

suggest that the program is well-aligned with students' academic needs and contributes meaningfully to their preparedness and confidence. Nevertheless, among the key areas evaluated, organizational and managerial aspects were identified as comparatively less robust. This stresses the need to enhance logistical coordination, scheduling efficiency, and administrative support mechanisms. Strengthening these components is essential to optimizing the overall implementation of the review program and ensuring its sustained effectiveness in supporting licensure examination readiness.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed for the Dean of the College of Education (CE):

1. prepare a comprehensive review schedule at the start of the term to avoid conflicts with regular academic activities and to ensure maximum student attendance.
2. assign the CE secretary to handle logistical arrangements, including room reservations and the preparation of needed equipment such as projectors, sound systems, and microphones for each session.
3. create a shared digital platform (e.g., Google Drive or FUEL LMS) where lecturers can upload PowerPoint presentations, handouts, and practice tests that are accessible to all student teachers.
4. conduct mid-program and post-program evaluations through surveys or focus group discussions to gather actionable student feedback for the continuous improvement of the review program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to ethical research standards to protect the rights, privacy, and welfare of all respondents. Before data collection, the research instrument and procedures were reviewed and approved by the College of Education to ensure alignment with institutional guidelines for ethical research conduct. Informed consents were obtained from all respondents through an introductory section of the Google Form survey, where the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and assurances of confidentiality were clearly explained. Participants were informed that their responses would be used solely for academic purposes and that no personal information would be collected or disclosed. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents had the option to decline without any academic or personal consequences. A 100% response rate was achieved, with all student teachers choosing to participate.

The data collected were stored securely in a password-protected digital environment via the Google platform and were accessible only to the researchers and the statistician. The anonymity of the participants was maintained throughout the study, and results were presented in collective form.

In the course of preparing this research, ChatGPT, an AI language model developed by OpenAI, was utilized as a tool for refining written content, generating initial drafts of research sections, and checking grammar and clarity. However, all final content was critically reviewed, validated, and revised by the researcher to ensure academic integrity, contextual appropriateness, and alignment with the objectives of the study. ChatGPT was not used to generate or analyze data, nor did it influence the formulation of findings and conclusions.

This study upholds the principles of respect for persons, in accordance with commonly accepted research ethics standards and the institutional policies of Foundation University.

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